

The Factors Influencing Patient Satisfaction in Interna Room Men Puncak Jaya Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Background: The satisfaction of services from hospitals can be judge requires adequate facilities, infrastructure and attitudes and behavior of health workers in providing services. Age and education of patients can assess the service they receive, the quality of service that has less implications for patient satisfaction.

Objective: To find out the factors that influence patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room Mulia Mulia Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency"

Research Method: Analytical with cross sectional study design. The population was all patients hospitalized during the months of October - December 2018 in the Male Nursing Room in Mulia Jaya Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency, as many as 109 samples. Data were obtained using questionnaires and analyzed using quare techniques and logistic regression.

Results: Factors that influence patient satisfaction in the Men's Nursing Room Mulia Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency are facilities (p-value 0.031; Rp: 1.781; CI95% (1,084 - 2,927), infrastructure (p-value 0,000; Rp. 4,861; CI95 % (2,758 - 8,570), behavior of health workers (p-value 0.001; Rp. 2,408; CI95% (1,586 - 3,657). Factors that not affect patient satisfaction in the Interna Room Men Mulia Mulia Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency are age (p-value 0.388; (RP: 1.293; CI95% (0.808 - 2.070), education (p-value 1,000; RP: 11.053; CI95% (0.626 - 1.774), length of stay (p-value 0.172; Rp. 1.462; CI95%; CI95% (0.903 - 2,366) The dominant factors that influence the satisfaction of male inpatients in Mulia Hospital are the facilities, infrastructure, attitudes and behavior of health workers.

Keywords: Satisfaction, Patient, Interna Room Men, Hospital

INTRODUCTION

Satisfaction is the level of one's feelings (customers) after comparing between performance or perceived results (services received and felt) with what he expected. A service is considered satisfactory if the service can meet the needs and expectations of the client. Satisfaction in the form of feeling happy or disappointed someone experienced after comparing the perceptions of performance or the results of a product with expectations (Nurjannah, 2012).

Some factors that influence patient satisfaction, depending on the characteristics of the patient include age and education, besides the facilities, infrastructure and attitudes and behaviors of health officers affect patient satisfaction such as helping and providing services to patients quickly, the ability of officers and the trustworthy nature possessed, the attention of doctors and nurses in providing services to patients and circumstances. The limitation factors that hospitals have in relation to human resources, funds and large available facilities are factors that significantly influence patient satisfaction (Lahinda, 2015; Andriani, 2017).

The Regional General Hospital is a type / class D hospital with 65 beds. Mulia Jaya Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency is currently in the preparation of accreditation which is planned to be implemented in

2020. One of the demands of accreditation is increasing patient satisfaction through improving quality services in accordance with standard operating procedures in providing health services in Mulia Jaya Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency. Therefore, Mulia Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency is required to be accredited in order to improve adequate facilities and infrastructure as well as specialist and non-specialist services. The results of preliminary studies at Mulia Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency, the number of inpatient visits in 2016 were 2,323 and in 2017 there were 2,210 people. This visit data showed a decrease in the number of patient visits but could not indicate patient satisfaction.

Based on the results of interviews on the initial data collection in July 2018 of the five patients, three patients complained about the services provided by health workers, due to insecurity and lack of empathy in serving staff, 2 other patients thought they were not comfortable with the conditions and physical facilities, such as building cleanliness and patient comfort. In addition, one informant said that service, especially at the counter, was still felt for a long time due to lack of information which caused the waiting time to be long in patient registration.

Based on this, patient satisfaction research as one of the features of hospital success is very important, because it can be used as feedback and input for improving the development of health services. Based on the description of the problem above, the authors are interested in conducting research with the title: "Factors that affect patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Jaya Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency".

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Type of Research

This study is an analytical study with a cross-sectional study approach, namely data collection is done simultaneously to find out the correlation between the variables studied

(Swarjana, 2013). This study was conducted to determine the effect of age, education, length of care, facilities, infrastructure, behavior of health workers on patient satisfaction.

2.2. Location and Time of Research

The study was conducted at Mulia Hospital and the time of the study was conducted in October - November 2018

2.3. Population and Samples

1. Population

Population is a generalization area consisting of: objects / subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics set by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn (Sugiyono, 2013). The population in this study were all male care room patients in October - December 2018 as many as 109 people.

2. Samples

The sample in this study was the total patients with the sampling technique in consecutive sampling, ie patients taken during stays in October - December 2018 obtained a sample of 109 people with criteria, namely families or patients who were treated or accompanied by patients at least 1 day.

3. RESULTS

Bivariate Analysis

a. Influence of Age with Patient Satisfaction

Table 1. Effect of Age with patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency in 2018

No	Age	Patient satisfaction					
		Not satisfaction		satisfy		Number	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
1	≤ 35 year	20	44,4	25	55,6	45	100
2	> 35 year	22	34,4	42	65,6	64	100
Number		42	38,5	67	61,5	109	100
<i>p-value</i> = 0,388; RP: 1,293; CI95% (0,808 – 2,070)							

Table 1 shows that of 45 people aged <35 years, 20 people (44.4%) were dissatisfied and respondents who were satisfied were 25 people (55.6%). Of the 64 respondents aged >35 years, 22 people (34.4%) were dissatisfied and respondents who were satisfied were 42 people (65.6%). The results of the chi square test obtained p-value 0.388 > α = 0.05 which stated that there was no significant effect between age

and patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Jaya Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency. Prevalence ratio test results (Rp. 1,293; CI95% (0,808 - 2,070) are interpreted as not meaningful because the lower values do not reach 1

b. Effect of Education with Patient Satisfaction

Table 2. The Influence of Education with patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency in 2018

No	Education	Patient satisfaction					
		Not satisfaction		Satisfy		Number	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
1	High (> SMA)	12	40	18	60	30	100
2	Basic (< SMA)	30	38	49	62	79	100
Number		42	38,5	67	61,5	109	100
<i>p-value</i> = 1,000; RP: 1,053; CI95% (0,626 – 1,774)							

Table 2 shows that of the 30 people who were further educated (<SMA) as many as 12 people (40%) were not satisfied and respondents who were satisfied were 18 people (60%). Of the 79 respondents with basic education 30 were (38%) dissatisfied and respondents who were satisfied were 49 people (62%). The chi square test results obtained $p\text{-value } 1,000 > \alpha = 0.05$ which stated that there was no significant effect between education on patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Jaya Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency. The prevalence ratio test results (RP: 11,053; CI95% (0,626 - 1,774) which are interpreted are not meaningful because the lower values do not include 1.

c. Effect of Length of Care with Patient Satisfaction

Table 3. The Influence of Education on Patient Satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency in 2018

No	Duration	Patient satisfaction					
		Not satisfaction		Satisfy		Number	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
1	> 3 days	24	46,2	28	53,8	52	100
2	< 3 days	18	31,6	39	66,4	57	100
Number		42	38,5	67	61,5	109	100
<i>p-value</i> = 0,172; RP: 1,462; CI95% (0,903 – 2,366)							

Table 3 shows that from 52 people who were treated for > 3 days, 24 people (46.2%) were dissatisfied and respondents who were satisfied were 28 people (53.8%). Of the 57 respondents whose length of stay <3 days

were 18 people (31.6%) were dissatisfied and respondents who were satisfied were 39 people (66.4%). The results of the chi square test obtained $p\text{-value } 0.172 > \alpha = 0.05$ which stated that there was no significant effect between length of stay on patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Jaya Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency. The prevalence ratio test results (RP: 1,462; CI95% (0,903 - 2,366) are interpreted as meaningless because the lower values do not include 1.

d. Effect of Facilities with Patient Satisfaction

Table 4. The influence of facilities with patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency in 2018

No	Facilities	Patient satisfaction					
		Not satisfaction		Satisfy		Number	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
1	Less	26	50	26	50	52	100
2	Good	16	28,1	41	71,9	57	100
Number		42	38,5	67	61,5	109	100
<i>p-value</i> = 0,031; RP: 1,781; CI95% (1,084 – 2,927)							

Table 4 shows that of 52 people stated that there were 26 people (50%) were not satisfied and 26 respondents (50%) were satisfied. Of the 57 respondents who stated that there were 16 good facilities (28.1%) were dissatisfied and 41% of respondents were satisfied (71.9%). The results of the chi-square test obtained $p\text{-value } 0.031 < \alpha = 0.05$ which stated that there was a significant influence between the means of patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Jaya Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency. The prevalence ratio test results (Rp. 1,781; CI95% (1,084 - 2,927) interpreted that the lack of facilities in the inpatient services tended to be dissatisfied patients with 1,781 times compared to respondents who stated good facilities.

e. Influence of Infrastructure with Patient Satisfaction

Table 5. Influence of Infrastructure with patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency in 2018

No	Infrastructure	Patient satisfaction					
		Not satisfaction		Satisfy		Number	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
1	Less	31	77,5	9	22,5	40	100
2	Good	11	15,9	58	84,1	69	100
Number		42	38,5	67	61,5	109	100
<i>p-value</i> = 0,000; RP: 4,861; CI95% (2,758 – 8,570)							

Table 5 shows that of the 40 people who stated that the infrastructure was less than 31 people (77.5%) were not satisfied and respondents who were satisfied were 9 people (22.5%). Of the 57 respondents who stated that there were 16 good facilities (28.1%) were dissatisfied and 41% of respondents were satisfied (71.9%). The chi square test results obtained p-value $0,000 < \alpha = 0.05$ which stated that there was a significant effect between infrastructure on patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Jaya Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency. Prevalence ratio test results (Rp. 4,861; CI95% (2,758 - 8,570) interpreted that the infrastructure that is less likely to be dissatisfied patients is 4,681 times compared to respondents who state good facilities.

f. Effect of Behavior of Health Workers with Patient Satisfaction

Table 6. Effects of Behavior of Health Workers on Patient Satisfaction in the Male Care Room at Mulia Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency in 2018

No	Behavior of Health Workers	Patient satisfaction					
		Not satisfaction		Satisfy		Number	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
1	Less	17	70,8	7	29,2	24	100
2	Good	25	29,4	60	70,6	85	100
Number		42	38,5	67	61,5	109	100
<i>p-value = 0,001; RP: 2,408; CI95% (1,586 - 3,657)</i>							

Table 6 shows that of the 40 people who stated that the behavior of health workers was less than 17 people (70.8%) were not satisfied and respondents who were satisfied were 7 people (29.2%). Of the 85 respondents who stated the behavior of good health personnel as many as 25 people (29.4%) were not satisfied and respondents who were satisfied were 60 people (70.6%). The chi square test results obtained p-value $0.001 < \alpha = 0.05$ which stated that there was a significant effect between the behavior of health workers on patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Jaya Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency. The prevalence ratio test results (RP: 2,408; CI95% (1,586 - 3,657) which are interpreted that the behavior of health workers who are less likely to be respondents are dissatisfied at 2,408 times compared to respondents who state good facilities.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Effect of Age with Patient Satisfaction

The results of the study showed that the majority of patients in the Male Care Room of Mulia Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency were mostly middle-aged (> 35) years old (58.7%. This was due to the fact that most respondents were patients who were being cared for to help patients most of them are > 35 years old. This research is in line with research conducted by Nurhidaya (2014) in Labuang Baji General Hospital Makassar that the majority of respondents were in middle-aged (> 35 years). In middle adulthood is a productive age, so patient demands are usually too high (Hatibie, 2015). A mature person will be more capable of making decisions, wiser, more able to think rationally, more able to control emotions with age. Age will affect someone in decision making. The rational maturity level possessed by the respondent is the capital in considering and thinking about the conditions currently being faced. Rational maturity helps respondents to assess satisfaction with the services used (Dessler, 2011).

Satisfaction responses of respondents aged <35 years were not satisfied with hospital services as much as 44.4% while those respondents aged > 35 said they were dissatisfied as much as 34.4% indicating that the same age group had the same chance of not being satisfied and satisfied with service given at Mulia Hospital and from the results of statistical tests it was stated that there was no effect of age on patient satisfaction at Mulia Hospital. The results of previous studies conducted by Hidayati, et al (2014) state the same research results that there is no influence between age and level of satisfaction. The absence of influence of age with satisfaction of patients at <35 years of age has a relatively low level of satisfaction compared with the age of > 35 years old because the age of more young adults is more productive has greater demands than young age. So that satisfaction is influenced

by what is known by the service that should be obtained from hospital services.

The results showed that the majority of respondents who were hospitalized in Mulia Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency, were 36-45 years old, 24 people (33.8%) or in middle adulthood and only a few >60 years old (3 years old). 4.2%). Patients who were more satisfied in patients aged 36-45 years (62.5%) and the lowest satisfaction in patients aged >60 years as much as 33.3%.

4.2 Effect of Education with Patient Satisfaction

The results of the study showed that most of the patients who were inpatient in the Manokawari General Hospital had a basic education (72.5%). Respondents with basic education were 40% dissatisfied and those with basic education stated that they were not as satisfied as 38%. This shows that at the level of education the respondent has the same tendency towards satisfaction that he receives at Mulia Hospital.

The statistical test results mean that there is no effect of education on the satisfaction of male inpatients at Mulia Hospital. The results of previous studies by Hidayati (2014) revealed the same thing that educating had no effect on satisfaction due to the presence of a stronger factor in patient satisfaction.

This study is in line with what was done previously by Kurniawan and Intiasari (2012), that the highest dissatisfied patients were patients with low education but the proportion was not much different from higher education. The results of Laurina et al., (2013) revealed that there was no influence between the level of education and patient satisfaction.

Education is the process of changing attitudes and behavior of a person or group of people in an effort to mature people through teaching and training efforts (Prayoto, 2014). Education means guidance given by someone to other people in order to understand something. It cannot be denied that the higher a person's education, the easier it is for them to receive information and in the end the more

knowledge they have. Conversely, if someone has a low level of education, it will hinder the development of the attitude of the person towards the acceptance of information and newly introduced values (Mubarak, 2011).

Patients with basic education who were dissatisfied were caused by a lack of understanding of the explanations given so that there could be a less precise interpretation of what was said or what was seen which caused dissatisfaction with the nurse's service. Higher educated patients tend to have more awareness of health status and the consequences of using health services.

4.3 Effect of Length of Care with Patient Satisfaction

Patients who were long inpatient at Mulia Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency were 47.7% > 3 days. Respondents who were long hospitalized in the Male Nursing Room > 3 days were 46.2% dissatisfied, while those who were treated for <3 days were 31.6% dissatisfied. The results of statistical tests stated that there was no significant effect between length of stay on patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Jaya Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency.

Another study at Dedy Jaya Brebes Hospital showed that of the 60 respondents taken from inpatient care, the majority of respondents were 43% in the category of failure, ie customers were not satisfied and were not loyal to nursing services, (Laksono, 2008). The research conducted by Anjaryani (2009) in Tugurejo General Hospital, there is a correlation between the characteristics of patients and patient satisfaction with nurse services in terms of length of treatment. Other studies at PKU Muhammadiyah Hospital in Bantul, in the inpatient and emergency rooms, showed different results, namely 70% of patients were satisfied with inpatient care while 80% of satisfaction was obtained in emergency services, the results of analysis of patient satisfaction showed a factor the highest determinants of satisfaction are success,

assurance, accessibility, responsiveness, tangible and empathy, (Wijayanti, 2009)

There is no effect on the duration of treatment due to the first day the patient is treated to feel the same as patients who have been treated for a long time. This equation causes a satisfaction assessment that is not different because it is caused by other factors that influence such as facilities, infrastructure, as well as officer attitudes and health behavior.

4.4 Effect of Facilities with Patient Satisfaction

A health service must pay attention to the facilities in providing good facilities to patients. This is done to attract patients in utilizing health services. Hospital service users, in this case patients, demand quality services not only concerning healing from physical illnesses or improving their health status, but also regarding satisfaction with attitudes, the availability of adequate facilities and infrastructure and a physical environment that can provide comfort. The respondent's statement challenged 52.3% of the facilities available in the Men's Nursing Room at RSUD Mulia Hospital, and 47.7% said they were lacking. The Respondent, which stated that the facilities were not the best, responded to the condition of running water, the cleanliness of the inpatient room and the condition of the equipment in the treatment. Whereas the general information, cleanliness and bedding of all respondents stated well. The results of statistical tests stated that the facilities had an effect on patient satisfaction in the Men's Care Room at Mulia Hospital. The results of the prevalence ratio test interpreted that the lack of facilities in the inpatient services tended to be dissatisfied patients at 1,781 times compared to respondents who stated good facilities. This study also agrees with previous researchers by Ahmad (2013) who conducted research in the Inpatient Room of the Regional General Hospital (RSUD) Daya Makassar that adequate facilities increased patient satisfaction.

The problem of facilities in patient complaints often occurs because of

unsatisfactory services, lack of water and health facilities are still very limited and other factors that affect patient satisfaction with the services provided by the hospital. Along with technological advances in the fields of medicine and health, the quality of quality services must also be improved. Customer satisfaction or patients are very important things that cannot be ignored by policy makers in the health sector. Water shortages occur in the RSUD Starting due to the absence of clean raw water institutions or managers for the community, where water sources are obtained from the river and wells. If during the dry season, water resources are obtained less and less, so that it affects the water needs of the hospital. Only in certain parts are prioritized like the operating room.

4.5 Influence of Infrastructure with Patient Satisfaction

The Mulia Regional General Hospital continues to develop and equip health infrastructure in accordance with the vision of RSUD Mulia to become the hospital of choice for the surrounding community in seeking and obtaining health services. As time goes by, the RSUD Milia faces strategic issues, namely not optimal health services; there are still patient complaints about existing services, lack of health service infrastructure. Health service infrastructure can be defined as a process of collaborating effectively and efficiently with all health infrastructures to provide professional services in the field of facilities and infrastructure in the process of effective and efficient health services also. Completeness of good infrastructure is very important in creating customer satisfaction (Febriani, 2012).

According to the technical guidelines for facilities and infrastructure in general inpatient building, including design guidelines, inpatient room requirements, technical requirements for inpatient building facilities, location, floor plan (minimum amount of space), building infrastructure technical requirements, building safety

requirements (Ministry of Health, Republic of Indonesia, 2012).

Respondents about the condition of the infrastructure mostly stated good as many as 69 people (63.3%). The good condition of the prescient stated by the respondent is the fulfillment of nutritional needs for patients, drug service in the pharmacy and administrative procedure services for patients. While patients who are not good are the condition of the equipment used by the staff in the service.

The condition of the equipment at Mulia Hospital is in accordance with hospital services in the type D category which is certainly not as complete as the higher-level sickness. In addition, from some observations that beebraap is part of the condition of damaged equipment, or limited other equipment that has an impact on health services optimally.

RSUD Mulia needs to routinely observe its services in order to maintain the strengths that exist and always improve the quality of service in variables that are still lacking in assessment or according to the patient's assessment not as expected by the patient, this can be done by paying more attention to the needs and patient's desire, improvement of facilities and infrastructure, guarantee of security, comfort, and trust and the promised service quickly, accurately and surely so that it will increase patient satisfaction.

4.6 Effects of Behavior of Health Workers with Patient Satisfaction

The quality of good service is not only measured by the luxury of facilities, the completeness of technology and physical appearance, but the attitude and behavior of employees must reflect professionalism and have high commitment. In practice, patient satisfaction surveys are conducted to improve the hospital environment, patient facilities and facilities in the context of consumerism. Effectiveness is measured based on patient feedback to improve health service providers' skills and practices that are still controversial. Respondents who stated that

the behavior of health workers was less as much as 70.8% were dissatisfied and respondents who stated the behavior of health personnel were good as many as 29.4% were dissatisfied. The results of statistical tests stated that there was a significant influence between the behavior of health workers with patient satisfaction and from the results of the prevalence ratio test interpreted that the behavior of health workers who were less likely to be dissatisfied respondents was 2.408 times compared to respondents who stated good facilities.

Respondents about the behavior of good health personnel are doctors / health workers responsive to patient complaints, skilled in serving patients, speed of action of doctors / officers appropriate in handling patients who need help, and providing free time to communicate with patients and provide explanations of medication and recommend re-check (re-control) if the complaint continues by providing a guarantee of recovery from service. Besides the responses of respondents stated that doctors / health personnel are patient in handling complaints. Respondents about the behavior of health workers is lacking is the speed of action of doctors / officers in accordance in dealing with patients who need help and doctors / officers friendly and polite in providing health services. Based on observations of patient dissatisfaction that is often found in relation to the attitudes and behavior of hospital staff due to communication problems, especially patients from the local area and the low education of patients, making it difficult for officers to explain the health problems faced by patients. This has an impact on respondents' responses to their lack of understanding and is impressed that doctors or other health workers are not friendly.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded as follows

1. There is no significant influence between age and patient satisfaction in the Male Care

Room of Mulia Jaya Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency (p-value 0.388; (Rp: 1,293; CI95% (0.808 - 2,070).

2. There is no significant effect between education on patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Jaya Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency (p-value 1,000; Rp: 11,053; CI95% (0,626 - 1,774).

3. There is no significant effect between length of stay on patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Jaya Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency (p-value 0.172; Rp. 1.462; CI95% (0.903 - 2,366).

4. There is a significant influence between the facilities on patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Jaya Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency (p-value 0.031; Rp: 1.781; CI95% (1,084 - 2,927).

5. There is a significant influence between infrastructure on patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room of Mulia Jaya Hospital in Puncak Jaya Regency (p-value 0,000; Rp. 4,861; CI95% (2,758 - 8,570).

6. There is a significant influence between the behavior of health workers on patient satisfaction in the Male Care Room in Mulia Jaya Hospital, Puncak Jaya Regency (p-value 0.001; Rp. 2.408; CI95% (1,586 - 3,657).

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